

THE ROLE OF INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS IN THE FOREIGN POLITICS OF MODERN UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This thesis reflects on the role of international economic organizations in foreign economic activities of Uzbekistan. Currently, several international economic organizations carry out their activities through mutual cooperation with states. In particular, Uzbekistan has also been working on membership and cooperation with several international organizations in recent years. For example, the World Trade Organization is an organization that is expected to become a member of Uzbekistan in the near future. We are all aware that Uzbekistan has its positive impact on the growth of both economic and legal potential.

Keywords: resolving international conflicts, legislative foundations, United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), military-political blocs, the UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) and etc.

The current stage of the development of international relations is characterized by the intensification of the process of globalization, regionalization and instability of political and economic situations in the world. It is increasingly possible to observe changes in the structure of the world economy, the development of new institutions in the field of regulating relations.

It is important to note the increasing role of national systems of regulation of international economic activity and international organizations. In fact, in such organizations, a small group of countries of the economic vanguard stands out, which enjoys the absolute right to make decisions, to influence the identified problems, to determine ways and methods of their settlement and to create a new investment regime, which creates a new order in the world.

The creation of many international organizations is conditioned by the task of preventing and resolving international conflicts. Over time, the peacekeeping activities of organizations are expanding, and diplomatic relations are becoming more complicated. At present, along with ensuring international security, efforts to resolve internal political conflicts are becoming increasingly important, and tasks to eliminate the causes of potential conflicts are also in the first place.

S. A. Galkin notes that an international organization is an association of countries established on the basis of an international treaty that carries out international cooperation based on its goals and objectives.¹

It is necessary for the international community to create such conditions of adaptation in which it would be possible to use globalization for the development of States and the interests of its citizens. The sphere of regulation of relations largely depends on international associations and organizations.

It is possible to single out the specific functions of international organizations:

- development of foreign economic relations;
- elimination of problems in trade and economic relations;
- stimulating the development of the private sector;
- assistance to other countries in resolving conflict situations;
- conducting a transparent economy.

International organizations play a global role in regulating trade and economic processes. Conflict smoothing, multilateral settlement, as well as unification of various kinds of documents, are the main problems of reaching agreement between East and West and solving common problems. However, all these goals cannot be solved under the influence of one country. It is necessary to reach agreement on general issues that simplify trade procedures and satisfy the interests of each country. It is also worth noting that the settlement of common problems of the East and the West will lead to mutual agreement and joint solution of problems. Which will ultimately prove to be more effective and productive for both sides.

From the first days of independence, Uzbekistan began to develop the conceptual and constitutional-legal foundations of its foreign policy, which laid the foundation for the establishment of foreign relations bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The conceptual and legislative foundations of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are constantly being improved based on new challenges and threats.

The foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan is based on the Constitution, the laws "On the Concept of Foreign Policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan" and "On international treaties" and other normative legal acts of the State, on statements and speeches by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and international conventions and treaties signed by the country.

The modern foreign policy of Uzbekistan is formed taking into account the dynamically changing international political realities of the XXI century, which require the implementation of an active, enterprising and pragmatic foreign policy course, timely and adequate response to emerging challenges.

¹ Galkin S. A. International economic relations. Basic parameters: handbook. – Moscow: «Весь мир», 2017, p. 43

The main objectives of the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan are further strengthening of the independence and sovereignty of the state, increasing the role and place of the country in international politics, creating the most favorable conditions for ensuring national and regional security, sustainable and dynamic development of the national economy, continuing the progressive movement towards building an open democratic state, joining the ranks of developed countries of the world.

In accordance with its Foreign Policy Concept, the Republic of Uzbekistan reserves the right to join alliances, to join the commonwealth and other interstate entities, as well as to leave them guided by the highest interests of the state, the people, their welfare and security, priority areas of modernization of the country, the current national legislation and international obligations.

Uzbekistan pursues a peaceful policy and does not participate in military-political blocs and reserves the right to leave any interstate formation in case it turns into a military-political bloc.

Our country takes political, economic and other measures to prevent its participation in military conflicts and hotbeds of tension in neighboring countries, and also does not allow the deployment of foreign military bases and facilities on its territory.

Uzbekistan is a member of such international organizations as the United Nations (UN), World Health Organization (WHO), International Labour Organization (ILO), Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD), World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO), Commonwealth of Independent States (CIS), International Telecommunication Union (ITU) and others.

These international organizations are very significant for the Republic of Uzbekistan. For example, one of the main organizations of which the Republic of Uzbekistan is considered a member is the UN. Now we will consider the role of this organization, that is, using the example of the UN, we will consider the role of international organizations in the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, in today's difficult conditions, against the background of the unprecedented growth of armed conflicts, threats to international peace and stability, the role and responsibility of the UN as a universal international structure is increasing, which is designed to unite the efforts of Member States in the name of strengthening peace and security, stability, protection of human rights and ensuring sustainable development.

On March 2, 1992, Uzbekistan became a Member of the United Nations, and since that day, the flag of our country has been flying at all UN residences, symbolizing the

republic's commitment to the proclaimed universal principles, values and goals. The relevant tasks for our country within the framework of the organization are non-proliferation of weapons of mass destruction, regional security, stabilization and reconstruction of Afghanistan, combating modern threats and challenges, promoting socio-economic development, solving environmental problems, in particular, mitigating the consequences of the Aral Sea crisis.

Uzbekistan, being a full member of the UN, demonstrates its commitment to the principle of equality, cooperation, multilateralism and protection of the international political system. In recent years, he has actively initiated the ideas of peaceful settlement of international conflicts, prevention of new global armed clashes, establishment of cooperation between countries, global dialogue, global actions and protection of human rights around the world.

An important step in the development of cooperation was the beginning of Uzbekistan's financing of projects within the framework of the UN. In particular, in 2018, voluntary contributions of 100 thousand US dollars were allocated to support the UN resident coordinator system, as well as the activities of the bureau of the Near East Agency for Relief and Works for Palestine Refugees (UNRWA), 120 thousand dollars - to the UNESCO fund. In 2020, a voluntary contribution of 100 thousand dollars was allocated to the United Nations Central Emergency Response Fund (CFRFS), in April 2021, the leadership of the republic decided to allocate a second aid to UNRWA in the amount of 100 thousand dollars. Currently, 137 specific projects totaling \$174.59 million are being actively implemented in Uzbekistan with the participation of UN agencies.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev notes that since its creation in 1945, the UN has become a truly universal international structure playing a central coordinating role in preserving peace and security on an international scale, ensuring sustainable development, protecting and promoting human rights.

Uzbekistan's candidacies for UN elected bodies are being actively promoted. During the elections held on October 13, 2020, Uzbekistan was elected a member of the Human Rights Council for the first time in its history, gaining 169 votes. In December 2021, the city of Samarkand was chosen as the venue for the 25th session of the UN World Tourism Organization General Assembly in 2023.

It is important to note the ongoing work to promote Uzbekistan's candidacy to the UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) for 2025-2027, the UNWTO Executive Council for 2023-2027, the UNESCO Executive Council for the period 2023-2027, the Intergovernmental Committee for the Protection of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of UNESCO (ICCN) for the period 2022-2026 and others.

According to the UN representatives, Uzbekistan's progress in recent years and its commitment to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) deserve high praise. There is no doubt that, as a firm supporter of lasting peace and initiator of comprehensive expansion of cooperation, Uzbekistan will continue to pay great attention to interaction with the UN and its member countries.

Another organization that we want to give as an example is CIS. In the rapidly changing situation in the world, the CIS, as a structure of interstate interaction, remains in demand as a mechanism for a permanent negotiation process, political dialogue, primarily at the highest level, and for developing coordinated positions to confront emerging new challenges and threats, and to resolve many acute issues of international security.

An extensive legal framework has been created within the CIS and tools and mechanisms of interaction have been developed in almost many areas of vital importance for the CIS member states, including such priorities as the further development of trade and economic relations, communication and transport links, security and humanitarian issues. The Commonwealth provides a broad opportunity to develop mutually acceptable approaches and coordinated practical measures aimed at timely and adequate response to challenges and threats to sustainable development, stability and security of the participating States, resolution of disputes and disagreements, for mutual communication of citizens in the CIS space.

Uzbekistan joined CIS on December 21, 1991. In Uzbekistan, the CIS is considered as a coordinating mechanism for multifaceted interaction and a platform for direct communication and maintaining interstate dialogue, including bilateral meetings in the CIS format, at the level of heads of countries and relevant structures, as well as an association of sovereign states interested in creating conditions for multilateral cooperation.

Our country stands for the formation of a full-fledged free trade zone in the CIS, based on principles that do not worsen the trade regime in force between the countries. This is becoming an important condition for ensuring stable socio-economic development in the CIS.

The Commonwealth can and should play the role of a coordinator of multifaceted interaction, become a platform for regulating economic processes in order to achieve maximum socio-economic effect for Uzbekistan.

Currently, Uzbekistan is developing cooperation with partners within the CIS in three dimensions: in the field of politics and security, economic and humanitarian spheres. The priority tasks are the formation of a full-fledged free trade zone and the strengthening of transport interconnectedness in the CIS space. Important attention is paid to joining efforts in the implementation of national programs and strategies aimed

at deepening industrial cooperation, ensuring food, energy and environmental security. In recent years, Uzbekistan has intensified its participation in the activities of the Commonwealth, signed more than 40 multilateral agreements, and joined 23 CIS sectoral bodies. In 2022, Uzbekistan's trade turnover with the CIS countries increased by a third, more than 1,000 joint ventures were created.

Uzbekistan is currently negotiating to join the WTO. The World Trade Organization is one of the priority organizations that strengthen international stability and increase the foreign economic activity of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of trade. Studying the issue of the Republic of Uzbekistan's accession to the World Trade Organization is necessary, since in the modern world international trade is a powerful catalyst for the economic growth of the country, contributing to the development of efficient production of goods and services, increasing the competitiveness of entrepreneurs and the inflow of foreign exchange funds into the national economy.

The World Trade Organization is an intergovernmental organization dealing with the liberalization of international trade, trade regulation and political relations, whose activities are based on an agreement signed on January 1, 1995. Today it is the largest international economic organization in the world, with 164 member States and providing 98% of world trade and world GDP. The main objective of the WTO is to ensure consistency and transparency of international trade by monitoring the state of the world economy. Entry into the membership of the international organization of the WTO is necessary for our country because the main objective of the WTO is to further liberalize world trade and ensure fair competition. Of course, the international organization of the WTO has a number of advantages and disadvantages, but this organization plays an important role for the foreign policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan. We wish our country to join the WTO as soon as possible.

Summing up, it can be summarized that the role of international organizations in international relations is quite large. This conclusion can be confirmed by the fact that international organizations are a sign of the globalization of the world. Formally, they do not interfere in the internal life of states, but in fact they have effective levers of pressure on the countries that are part of these associations. Uzbekistan's active participation in the work of international organizations is an urgent and useful form of foreign policy activity that contributes to the more effective achievement of foreign policy goals and objectives.

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